

PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED LEGAL VOCABULARY IN LINGUISTICS AND METHODOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219301>

Abstract. *Features of reading as a speech activity make it a very effective learning tool. Its positive role in the assimilation of language material is significant: the mnemonic activity that accompanies the reading process ensures that students memorize the learned and new units of the language. Therefore, at advanced stages of learning, reading texts is one of the means of expanding vocabulary.*

Key words: *semantic, illustrative, stylistic, receptive, pragmatic, strategic, paradigmatic, consolidating, perceptual, sociocultural.*

The emergence of special-professional communication is directly related to the development of human society. In the course of work, special-professional communication is carried out. The word term is always the result and means of professional thinking and special professional communication.

Terminology has a long history, but the concept of "term" in science was formed at the beginning of the 20th century. "Encyclopedic dictionary" Brockhouse F. A. and Efron I. A. defines terms and terminology as follows: "A term is a word that corresponds to a certain concept, is separated or included in a judgment or conclusion ... Scientific terms ... are words that have a strictly defined special meaning in a certain field of science. A set of terms firmly established in a particular science constitutes the terminology of a particular science" (Brockhouse, Efron, 1901: 957-958).

The modern "Philosophical dictionary" defines the term as "a single word that defines a certain concept of science, technology, art, etc." This term is an element of the language of science, and its introduction is related to the need to clearly and accurately define scientific information, especially information that does not have corresponding names in ordinary language. Unlike words in ordinary language, terms are devoid of emotional meaning. (Philosophical Dictionary, 1991: 456).

Studies in the field of terms and terminology in Russian linguistics D. S. Started with Lotte's activities. G. Filimonova D.S. Summarizing Lotte's contribution to the study of terminology, he is called the founder of the Russian terminological school. He was one of the first to use a systematic approach to terminology. His school developed requirements for the term such as accuracy, precision, consistency, lack of synonyms, brevity, etc. (Filimonova, 1995: 90)

From I.R. Halperin's point of view, terms are words those denote emerging concepts related to the development of science, technology, and art. The terms have mostly no emotional meaning, although in some cases they may have a certain emotional color in the text. Their monosemic feature defines terms. By their nature, they are more resistant to the process of growth with additional meanings. (Halperin, 1958: 58)

G.O. Vinokura's works contributed greatly on the development of the technical assignment.. He raised a number of questions that are still the focus of researchers (the linguistic essence of the term, the nature and organization of terms). G.O. Vinokur notes that:

- 1) Specialization of its meaning, clarity of semasiological boundaries;

2) Its intellectual purity, that is, its detachment from emotional experiences. (Vinokur, 1939)

R.A. Budagov noted the same characteristic features in the semantics of the term: A term is a word with a strictly defined meaning. As a rule, the term has one meaning. More precisely, the term tends to monosemy" (Budagov, 1965: 29). The following definition is also given in the previous work of the same author: "The term differs from words only in its tendency to monosemy. The term is also devoid of emotional tones" (Budagov. 1947: 24).

According to A. A.Reformatsky, terms are special words limited to a special meaning, words that tend to be unambiguous as the precise expression of the names of concepts and things. (Here we can recall that the word "term" it comes from the Latin terminus, which means "boundary mark, limit, and border"). Later A. A. Reformatsky argues that terms exist not only in language, but also as part of a certain terminology (Reformatsky, 2006: 410).

However, in recent years, Lotte D.S. began to suspect that the requirements of the term formulated by (Golovin, 1971: 64-67) Viewing this term as "a word or phrase of a special (scientific, technical, etc.) language created (adopted, derived, etc.) to clearly express special concepts and designate special objects." (Akhmanova, 1966: 474), that it was seriously criticized as a special lexical unit (for example, in the works of B. N. Golovin). It is emphasized that the term is not a special type of the lexical unit, but a function, a special type of use of the lexical unit. As early as 1939, O. Vinokur "any word can perform the function of a term..., terms are not special words, but only words with a special function." (Vinokur, 1939:5). This idea is actively developed by modern research on terms. Thus, A.A. Bragina says that many terms are simple words, "as if taken from their usual paradigm, devoid of usual connotative links." (Bragina, 1986: 58) The term cannot be separated from the language. Directly, the term always preserves its internal form. Entering the system of special terms, the word allegedly breaks the connection with the general language system, "shakes off old connotations, background shades of meaning, breaks away from expressive understanding and enters the system of special language signs artificially created by man to distinguish the phenomena of science, technology, art." But at the same time, the possibility of restoring the previous shades of meaning remains. "At any convenient moment, this term can come to life and "erase" the strict ambiguity of old and new concepts, "unacceptable" shades in it." (Bragina, 1986: 58)

By the following I.R. Galperin, we believe that two processes are at work in the formation of the term and its "subsequent fate":

a) the process of forming a new term from the common vocabulary, Latin and Greek morphemes, assimilations.

b) gradual determinology, i.e. gradual loss of terminological meaning, overgrowth of a bunch of derived meanings, loosening of solidity in the semantic structure" (Galperin, 1958: 61)

for example, such words as telephone, radio, electricity have completely lost their terminological coloring.

Thus, there is a constant connection between terminological and general literary vocabulary. At the same time, there is some caution in the definition of the term, which is associated with the lack of clarity in distinguishing terminological lexicon from non-terminological lexicon, recognized by many modern researchers (Bragina A.A., Razinkina N.M., etc.). This attitude is reflected in the definition of the term, in which "Linguistics" Big encyclopedic dictionary, 1998. A term is a word or phrase that expresses the concept of a special field of knowledge or activity. The term enters the general lexical

system of the language, but only through a certain terminological system (terminology). Features of the term include:

- 1) Consistency;
- 2) Availability of definition (for many terms);
- 3) A tendency to monosemy within a specific terminological field, that is, the terminology of a certain science...;
- 4) lack of expression;
- 5) Stylistic neutrality.

These features of the term are implemented only in the terminological field, outside of which the term loses its specific and systematic properties "(Large encyclopedic dictionary" Linguistics, 1998: 508-509)

From the point of view of R. Yu. Kobrin determining the differentiated signs of terms, the division of the lexicon into terminological and non-terminological is carried out intuitively by the native speaker. Because of a series of experiments, the author identified the following differential features of the terms:

- ◆ ◆ nominative;
- ◆ ◆ functional-semantic specificity is expressed in the nominalization of the meaning and limitation of the scope of activity by the texts of a certain field of knowledge.
- ◆ ◆ structural and grammatical specificity; expressed in the non-predicative nature of phrases; dividing coordinating phrases into constituent parts, dividing text segments into parts, including subjects and predicates, verb groups, participles, adverbial and subordinate constructions.

R. Yu. Kobrin says that in most cases these features are implicitly perceived signs of terms. But, nevertheless, they serve as a basis for classifying a text unit as a term. (Kobrin, 1997: 34-41)

This approach to defining what a term is seems to be the most reasonable, as it is directly related to linguistic reality. As a final definition of the term, we use Kobrin R.Yu. and B. N. Golovin's "Linguistic foundations of the teaching of terms", "A term is a word or subordinate phrase that has a special meaning, expresses and forms a professional concept, and is used in the process of knowing and developing scientific and professional objects and the relations between them" (Golovin, Kobrin, 1987 : 9) we can stop at the formula given in the work. Accordingly, terminology is a set of terms related to the field of professional activity (knowledge, technology, management, culture), connected to each other at the conceptual, lexical-semantic, word formation and grammatical levels. (Golovin, Kobrin; 1987:11)

The basic unit of terminology (its smallest component) is the word. The word, in turn, is the smallest semantic unit of the language, which is freely repeated in speech to build speech. Terms and terms are semantic units of language that are freely repeated in speech, they have integrity and extrusion, they are the smallest units of language that are freely repeated in speech, participate in the construction of sentences, that is, they are used for communication purposes.

According to current views about the conceptual content of terms and commonly used words, commonly used words represent general ideas or everyday concepts, while terms represent specialized-professional scientific or technical concepts. According to the view of T.A. Juravleva, we believe that general ideas, everyday concepts, and special professional concepts can be expressed in terms of the materiality of reflected features as follows.

Scheme 1. General ideas, everyday concepts, special concepts

The term of any field of knowledge if it is used in the context of special professional communication; expresses a special professional concept (scientific or technical) in written texts

or in the written speech of experts. The term that works in the context of everyday communication or in literary texts expresses a general idea, and the border between the everyday concept and the general idea is quite arbitrary, it consists of the level of materiality of the reflected features: the everyday concept is characterized by a high level of tolerance, approximation, closeness to the features of the object. In turn, the term differs from the everyday concept by the greater materiality of the reflected properties of the object, the degree of penetration into the essence of the reflected objects.

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